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II: Where the Racial Contract and the New Jim Crow Collide

Our life is dictated by social, moral, and political norms and expectations. Some of these things are forced upon us by government systems while others are formed within culture and community. The social contract is a moral and political philosophical thought experiment that tackles this idea and has been very influential to modern political philosophy. Charles Mills wrote *the Racial Contract* as a critique of the social contract which introduces the idea that the contract was written within a pre-established Racial Contract that shaped future systems and societies from then on. While a racial hierarchy was already at work within current systems, the social contract was a tool that helped shape systems of power from that point on. We are able to see the Racial Contract in our own country, and more importantly, how it has been rewritten multiple times. In Michelle Alexander's *The New Jim Crow*, she analyzes our current justice system and how it mirrors our country's past. This has always been difficult for white America to observe and digest because of the epistemological challenges that they face and because they are the very individuals for whom the Racial Contract was written. By partnering Mills' and

Alexander's work, we are able to tackle the true depth of our white American polity and its hold over our government systems today.

To delve into mass incarceration, we must first familiarize ourselves with the Racial Contract. The social contract is a thought experiment that constructs the origins of why we today have and need systems of power. Some contract theorists focus on the moral contract while others focus on the political contract. The moral contract has an objective moral truth by which we all abide in the state of nature and within this context, systems are created. Political contracts, on the other hand, create these norms or truths only once you have left the state of nature. Mills focuses primarily on the moral contract when presenting the Racial Contract. While the social contract is a thought experiment, Mills highlights how the act of leaving the state of nature is done by the white polity. He explains how the role of the state of nature changes with this understanding and says, "In the white settler state, its role is not primarily to demarcate the (temporarily) pre-political state of "all" men (who are really white men), but rather the permanently pre-political state or, perhaps better, non-political state (insofar as "pre-" suggests eventual internal movement toward) of nonwhite men. The establishment of society thus implies the denial that a society already existed; the creation of society requires the intervention of white men, who are thereby positioned as already socio-political beings."²⁸ For many philosophers, they compared the state of nature to the native Americans and their savageness for example. This does not mean that the state of nature as it functions in the contract is synonymous with non-white people for two reasons. One, white people were hypothetically in the state of nature at some point and left it to be able to form their society. Two, non-white people are unable to leave the state of nature without the help of the white polity. In understanding this, we can see how the social contract was never intended to include, and more specifically, to be used by non-white

²⁸ Charles W. Mills, *The Racial Contract*, (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1997), 25.

people to form their own polity. Non-white people are permanently pre-political and therefore, the maintenance of white supremacy is required for the social contract and body politic to form and function. From this, we get the rewriting of the contract to perpetuate the subordination of non-white people.

The New Jim Crow written by Michelle Alexander presents how our system today functions as a new-age racial caste system in America. She outlines the history of Jim Crow and slavery in America as well as reviews policy that propelled the formation of the New Jim Crow and how it affects African Americans today. Alexander starts by reviewing the reconstruction era as the death of slavery that came after the 13th Amendment which abolished slavery, the 14th Amendment for the protection of due process, and the 15th Amendment for the right to vote, amongst other civil rights laws. The Reconstruction Era then led to the birth of Jim Crow due to outrage and fear from white America that African Americans would rise to power. This is the first step towards our modern-day racial caste system and Alexander explains that,

Once again vagrancy laws and other laws defining activities such as “mischief” and “insulting gestures” as crimes were enforced vigorously against blacks. The aggressive enforcement of these criminal offenses opened up an enormous market for convict leasing, in which prisoners were contracted out as laborers to the highest private bidder...tens of thousands of African Americans were arbitrarily arrested during this period, many of them hit with court costs and fines, which had to be worked off in order to secure their release. With no means to pay off their “debts,” prisoners were sold as forced laborers to lumber camps... Convicts had no meaningful legal rights... They were understood, quite literally, to be slaves of the state. The Thirteenth Amendment to the U.S. Constitution had abolished slavery but allowed one major exception: slavery remained appropriate as punishment for a crime.²⁹

This Rise of Jim Crow is the blueprint that will be mimicked from now on and is extremely important in understanding mass incarceration as a racial caste system. The death of Jim Crow happened for many reasons: more African Americans were moving north and gaining political

²⁹ Michelle Alexander and Cornel West, *The New Jim Crow: Mass Incarceration in the Age of Colorblindness* (New York, NY: New Press, 2020), 32.

influence, The NAACP was fighting for the protection of Black Americans, *Brown v Board of Education*, and Nazi regime of the Second World War led to embarrassment and questioning of the United States as the “free world” and its credibility due to its ever-present racial hierarchy. This all pushed for the second Reconstruction Era. There was a wave of social movements that all became criminalized and “law and order” quickly smacked down any potential for Black liberation. The movement, support, idea, or empowerment of Black people all became a threat to law and order. To protest was to stand in opposition to American security, leading to the criminalization of the Black body furthermore. This threat then birthed the War on Drugs and different laws that formed the fast track to second-class status. We have finally reached our current day justice system and have not even scratched the surface.

The racing or norming of space for Mills is a leading factor in the Racial Contract and we can see this today in our justice system. Mills explains that you associate any given group to a space and apply certain characteristics to them so when thinking about the space, you connect it to a group of people. In this context, this association is based on race. Mills defines it as, “a circular indictment: You are what you are in part because you originate from a certain kind of space, and that space has those properties in part because it is inhabited by creatures like yourself.”³⁰ The body and the space are equivalent. You are associated with that space and also assumed to fully occupy it. This is apparent in the surge of “tough on crime” politicians following the Civil Rights Movement. Alexander states, “In the words of Representative John Bell Williams, ‘This exodus of Negroes from the South, and their influx into the great metropolitan centers of other areas of the Nation, has been accompanied by a wave of crime... What has civil rights accomplished for these areas?... Segregation is the only answer as most

³⁰ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 51.

Americans—not the politicians.”³¹ The association of Black people with crime and linking it with the notion that physical separation is the only solution is a perfect example of the racing of space. The result is that crime and Black people become synonymous.

The mirroring of our past and re-writing the contract is addressed by Alexander head-on. She says,

Indeed, a primary function of any racial caste system is to define the meaning of race in its time. Slavery defined what it meant to be black (a slave), and Jim Crow defined what it meant to be black (a second-class citizen). Today mass incarceration defines the meaning of blackness in America: black people, especially black men, are criminals. That is what it means to be black.³²

If we think about this in a hypothetical or ideal way, for one to be a criminal, one must commit a crime. We now understand that once you have raced the space, you do not need to do anything except be Black in America. Alexander explains, “Many offenders are tracked for prison at early ages, labeled as criminals in their teen years, and then shuttled from their decrepit, underfunded inner city schools to brand-new, high-tech prisons.”³³ We will look more into how this functions later but as a basic understanding, there is no action required, and there is no moving out of this criminal status. It is permanent—similar to being in the state of nature for non-white people. At a young age, you are seen as deviant, criminal, and trying to succeed under this assumption, which is an unrealistic expectation.

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³¹ Alexander and Cornel, *The New Jim Crow: Mass Incarceration in the Age of Colorblindness*, 40.

³² Alexander and Cornel, *The New Jim Crow: Mass Incarceration in the Age of Colorblindness*, 197.

³³ Alexander and Cornel, *The New Jim Crow: Mass Incarceration in the Age of Colorblindness*, 150.

The criminalization of non-white people is a result of the idea of sub-persons as they relate to the superior race. There are two key ways that help us understand how racial superiority came about. First, the “sub” is needed to create the “person” so non-white people are directly a part of the white polity. Two, the normative features of our society and culture are all linked to personness which is whiteness. For the first point, Mills says, “For these are identities as ‘contrapuntal ensembles,’ requiring their opposites, with the ‘secondariness’ of sub-persons being, as Said phrases it, ‘paradoxically, essential to the primariness of the European.’”³⁴ A contrapuntal ensemble is a musical term to describe when two independent melodies are paired in order to create a new harmonious tune. As this “new tune” is the white polity, whiteness needs non-whiteness to function in the Racial Contract. In contrast, non-whiteness does not need Whiteness to function, for non-whiteness was forced into the position to create the sub-person. Mills describes the second point by saying,

Europeans and their descendants, continue to benefit from the Racial Contract, which creates a world in their cultural image, political states differentially favoring their interests, an economy structured around the racial exploitation of others, and a moral psychology (not just in whites but sometimes in nonwhites also) skewed consciously or unconsciously toward privileging them, taking the status quo of differential racial entitlement as normatively legitimate, and not to be investigated further.³⁵

The Racial Contract was structured in such a way that handcuffed non-white people to it, therefore, preventing them from removing themselves from it in the eyes of white people. Being non-white means that you can never achieve normativity and there is no level of success or power that will separate you from your sub-personhood.

A system created around the subordination of a certain race requires maintenance and repair. The Racial Contract would be expected to be challenged, rejected, or thrown out due to the expectation that people will begin to recognize it. That is why the Racial Contract is rewritten

³⁴ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 66.

³⁵ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 50.

and functions as a moving target to uphold the white polity to this day. We are not living in the aftermath of America's racist past but rather experiencing the new contract. In Cayna Laurene Sharp's dissertation, she presented this act of re-writing in her analysis of Mills and Alexander. In explaining Alexander's historical review of specifically "law and order," Sharp says, "Here we can see the work of the Racial Contract, being rewritten and reconstructed in order to conform to shifting attitudes about race and morality. It was no longer acceptable to explicitly call someone a criminal because they were Black, but it certainly was safe and morally just to assume to oneself that anyone who is Black is a criminal."³⁶ The morality and epistemology of the white polity remain constant in the way that it deems its subordination of non-white people as justified. In Alexander's introduction, she told the story of Mr. Cotton which Sharp also highlighted. Mr. Cotton looked back at four family generations of men in America and today, he is a felon. Every point in history, white people saw it as acceptable for the given right to be removed. How our system ensures second-class status is not what the Racial Contract focuses on, but rather as long as it maintains the person-to-subperson relationship. Mills says "an

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epistemology of ignorance, a particular pattern of localized and global cognitive dysfunctions (which are psychologically and socially functional), producing the ironic outcome that whites will in general be unable to understand the world they themselves have made."³⁷ This epistemology looks delusional and backward but is intentional. The Racial Contract is set up to be normative,

³⁶ Cayna Laurene Sharp, "White Supremacy and the Racial Contract in the United States," *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*, (University of Memphis Digital Commons, 2020), 2079, <https://digitalcommons.memphis.edu/etd/2079>, 62.

³⁷ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 30.

objective, singular, and primary. Our current system of mass incarceration is described as “genius” by Alexander for it allows for the illusion that people of color can work their way out of sub-personhood by obeying the law. Our current contract puts the blame and responsibility on the sub-person and while that is unique from past contracts, it exceeds the person-to-sub-person subordination.

Today, our newest edition of the Racial Contract has only continued the oppression of the Black body. We have reviewed what the contract is and how our country’s white polity has behaved. We have analyzed how the natural, moral, and epistemological claims require that the contract is maintained. There is no better example for explaining Mills’ Racial Contract than seeing how his claims reign true by turning to the system we all live under today. Mills states, “The coercive arms of the state, then—the police, the penal system, the army—need to be seen as in part the enforcers of the Racial Contract, working both to keep the peace and prevent crime among the white citizens, and to maintain the racial order and detect and destroy challenges to it, so that across the white settler states nonwhites are incarcerated at differential rates and for longer terms.”³⁸ Terry Stops, plea bargaining, and minimum sentencing are all legal practices that are seen as acceptable and support racial disparities in our justice system. Wealth inequality, housing discrimination, and the public school-to-prison-pipeline play a huge part in positioning non-white Americans to fail. The thing that perpetuates all of these things is being labeled a felon. Alexander explains,

Once you’re labeled a felon, the old forms of discrimination—employment discrimination, housing discrimination, denial of the right to vote, denial of educational opportunity, denial of food stamps and other public benefits, and exclusion from jury service—are suddenly legal. As a criminal, you have scarcely more rights, and arguably less respect, than a black man living in Alabama at the height of Jim Crow. We have not ended racial caste in America; we have merely redesigned.³⁹

³⁸ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 91.

³⁹ Alexander and Cornel, *The New Jim Crow: Mass Incarceration in the Age of Colorblindness*, 2.

This redesigning is the main conclusion for Mills and also for Alexander. In America, the Racial Contract holds up the white polity through the assignment of a felon status. Being labeled a felon, as described above, is equivalent to being Black in the Jim Crow era. During that time, segregation was considered completely acceptable, and now the restricting of one's rights for being a felon is also considered completely acceptable. Our justice system today is a perfect example of the rewriting of the Racial Contract and the New Jim Crow best explains it.

Mills referenced the Holocaust multiple times mainly to show that the same things that were done in the Global South or during colonization were then done to Europeans. We saw the widespread condemnation of the Nazi Regime, political reform, reparations, cultural opinion shifting, and global recognition of the horrific crimes. It is clear that we are capable of tearing up the Racial Contract, but the question remains whether or not people are willing to do so. Both Mills and Alexander conclude that we must have a shift in public opinion through education. This does not mean simply seeing how today's system fails, but rather an understanding of the Racial Contract, its rewriting, and how they have shaped every aspect of our life white and non-white. If we can change public opinion so far that we shift the normative narrative from the white polity, we will be able to be rid of the contract, which would then unravel all of its enforcers.